

potassium hydroxide solution canary yellow needles were obtained.

The compounds produced vivid colours (orange to brown) when treated with conc. sulphuric acid. The presence of α , β -unsaturated ketonic group was ascertained by absorption bands near 1661 to 1680 cm^{-1} in the infrared absorption spectrum of these compounds. All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C and H elements.

The antimicrobial activity of these compounds was tested by Zone inhibition techniques with *S. aureus* using benzoic acid as standard. All the compounds were found to be less active than standard.

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Chemical Examination of the Inflorescence of *Ocimum kilimandscharicum* Gurke

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OCIMUM kilimandscharicum commonly known as 'bantulsi' belongs to the family *Labiatae*. A sweet smelling bush it grows wild with long decorative inflorescences. In view of its commercial importance in India as a source of camphor, the plant has been extensively studied¹⁻⁴ on various aspects including chemistry. The present work deals with the chemical investigation of the inflorescence which has not been reported so far.

1077 g of air-dried mature inflorescence was steam distilled to remove the volatile fraction. This weighed 3.5 g from which 0.4 g of camphor crystallised out. The inflorescence left after steam distillation was extracted with rectified spirit in a soxhlet apparatus. The alcohol-free extract was repeatedly washed with ether. The ether washings were divided into neutral and acidic fractions.

The neutral fraction contained 32.2 g of a light yellow oil which was saponified with 10% alcoholic caustic soda. The nonsaponifiable portion weighed 1.2 g. This on chromatography gave a crystalline-sterol from the benzene fraction (yield 0.2 g). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p.

138°C, $[\alpha]_D - 36$ (chloroform). It gave an acetate, m.p. 124°C and a benzoate, m.p. 144°C. The sample was established as β -sitosterol from comparison of mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

The acidic fraction, a light brown solid weighing 32.6 g gave a violet colour, with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent and was triterpenic in nature. 10 g of this acid was esterified with diazomethane and the crude ester was chromatographed over alumina. Since no satisfactory separation of the constituent esters could be obtained from this chromatography, the different fractions were mixed together and acetylated with pyridine and acetic anhydride on water bath. The acetylated methyl esters, however, separated nicely on chromatography over alumina. Fraction A (yield 2.8 g) appeared in the benzene eluent in a crystalline form. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 217-19°C. It gave a violet colour with L.B. reagent and produced yellow colour with tetranitromethane. On alkaline hydrolysis it furnished a methyl ester, m.p. 198°C, $[\alpha]_D + 72$ (chloroform). The compound was identified as methyl oleanolate from mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample. Fraction B (yield 0.6 g) came in the tail runs of the benzene eluent and crystallised from alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 245-46°C. It also responded to both L.B. reagent and tetranitromethane. On hydrolysis it gave a methyl ester, m.p. 170°C, $[\alpha]_D + 56$ (chloroform). The compound was identified as methyl ursolate from a mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample.

The inflorescence of *O. kilimandscharicum* was thus found to contain 0.04% camphor, 0.02% β -sitosterol, 0.86% oleanolic acid and 0.18% ursolic acid.

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The Use of *p*-Rosaniline as Diazo Coupling Component for Azoic Dyes

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THOUGH basic dyes are well known for their high tinctorial value as well as brightness, they have been found to be much less resistant to the action of light and soap. The 'naphthols' have been known for good fastness but they lack brightness. We have therefore tried to combine the two by using the basic dye as an amine to be diazotised and coupled with 'naphthols'. In this paper we have reported the diazotisation of *p*-rosaniline and the fastness of shades obtained therefrom.

The diazotisation was easily done by the acid-sodium nitrite process. However, it was not possible to obtain two sets of dyes—monoazo and bisazo—even though *p*-rosaniline contained two amino groups. Both were simultaneously diazotised.

The dyeing on cotton hanks, mercerised or unmercerised were carried out in the usual manner of azoic dyeing. The results of the fastness tests—soaping, rubbing, bleaching and action of light have been given in Table 2.

The study of shades and fastness properties have shown that a variety of deep shades can be obtained in this way. Fastness to chlorine is moderate while that to light is varying, depending upon the naphthol used. There is an improvement in fastness to soaping and light as compared to the dyeing by basic dyes. The combination does not give very bright

shades except on mercerised yarn. Amongst the combinations to shade obtained from Naphthol AS-SB and diazotised *p*-rosaniline gives very deep shade which is very fast to soaping, bleaching and has maximum light fastness.

Experimental

p-Rosaniline base (1 g) is dissolved in water (25 ml) containing hydrochloric acid (2.2 ml), sodium nitrite solution (14 ml; 0.5*N*) is added slowly to the cooled solution (10°C). It was then neutralised by sodium acetate solution.

The naphthol is purified and dissolved according to the standard method of pasting with turkey red oil and 20% alkali followed by dilution with hot water.

TABLE 1. DYES FROM *p*-ROSANILINE

Sl. No.	Naphthol used	Colour	M.P. °C	Crystallisation	Analysis (nitrogen)	
					Found	Calc.
1.	Naphthol AS	Red	253-54	Microscopic needles from ethylene dichloride	11.8	11.7
2.	-do- AS-D	Red	255	-do-	11.0	11.3
3.	-do- AS-SG	Deep violet	Above 300	Violet dye from chlorobenzene.	11.6	11.8
4.	-do- AS-ITR	Red	242	Red dye from chlorobenzene.	9-3	9.6
5.	-do- AS-G	Yellow	No m.p.	Yellow dye from chlorobenzene.	11.5	11.8
6.	-do- AS-L ₃ G	Yellow	-do-	-do-	8.6	8.8
7.	-do- AS-BO	Red	261	Red dye from chlorobenzene.	11.9	11.6
8.	-do- AS-GR	Maroon	270	Maroon dye from chlorobenzene.	10.0	10.2
9.	-do- AS-LB	Brown	Above 300	Brown dye from chlorobenzene.	12.4	12.8

TABLE 2. SHOWING FASTNESS OF SHADES (Base : *p*-Rosaniline)

Sl. No.	Naphthol	Shade	% Shade	Fastness to			
				Washing	Rubbing	Chlorine	Light
1.	Naphthol AS	Red	1	5	4	3-4	5
2.	-do- AS-D	-do-	1	5	4	3	5-6
3.	-do- AS-SG	Black	1	5	4	5	7-8
4.	-do-	Deep blue	0.5	5	4	4	7
5.	-do- AS-S	Red	1	4	4	3	5-6
6.	-do- AS-L ₃ G 50% + AS-SG 50%	Olive brown	1	4	4	2	3
7.	-do- AS-ITR	Red	1	5	4-5	2	5
8.	-do- AS-G	Yellow	1	4	4-5	3	3
9.	-do- AS-L ₃ G	-do-	1	4	4	3	5
10.	-do- AS-BO	Red	1	5	4	3	6
11.	-do- AS-Gr	Deep violet	1	5	4	3	4
12.	-do- AS-LB	Reddish brown	1	4-5	4-5	3	3
13.	-do- AS-SG (25%) + AS-G (75%)	Violetish brown	1	4-5	4	3	3
14.	-do- AS-ITR (8.3%) + AS-G (91.7%)	Reddish yellow	1	4-5	4	3	3
15.	-do- AS-SG (16.6%) + AS-G (83.4%)	-do-	1	4-5	4	3	3
16.	-do- AS-ITR (50%) + AS-G (50%)	Red	1	4-5	4	3	.

NOTES

The dye is obtained by adding the diazotised solution to a cooled solution of the naphthol, it is purified through high boiling solvents like chlorobenzene and analysed for nitrogen. Colour, m.p. and other properties are given in Table 1.

Dyeing: It was carried out in the usual way for azoic dyeing—temp. of the bath 60°C and material—liquor ratio of 1 : 20. After thirty minutes the hank was squeezed and passed through neutral diazotised *p*-rosaniline solution. After boiling with 1% soap solution for half an hour, it is dried and tested for fastness to soaping, bleaching, rubbing and light. The action of soap solution (8 g/litre) at 90–100°C for thirty minutes was studied. The shade not affected at all was graded as 5 and that with poor resistance as 1. The conditions for rubbing and light fastness tests are the same as those described by us in the previous communications¹, the only difference being that light fastness was determined in a Fade-o-meter.

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Phenolic Aldoximes as Indicators for the Direct NTA Titration of Iron

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THE substances reported in literature as indicators for the direct titration of ferric ions with nitrilo-triacetic acid (NTA) are chromeazurole-S¹, pyrocatechol violet², and N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine³. The present article reports the use of salicylaldoxime and β -resoreylaldoxime as indicators for the direct NTA titration of ferric ions.

Both these substances give violet colour with ferric ions. The endpoint is a sharp colour change from violet to yellow on titration with NTA. The optimum pH range is 1.5–2.5. Addition of four drops of 1.0% indicator solution gives satisfactory results. The titration can be satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 15–50°C. The end point can be detected even in 1 ml of 0.001M solution of ferric nitrate, thus microtitration with NTA is feasible with these indicators.

The titrations of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.0. At 2.8 mg concentration of iron, 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of Be²⁺ and UO₂²⁺, 25 times excess of Pd²⁺, 10 times excess of Ag⁺,

5 times excess of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Al³⁺, Ni²⁺, Mg²⁺, and twice the excess of Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cr³⁺, Co²⁺, could be tolerated. Cu²⁺, Th⁴⁺, Zn⁴⁺ and anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Synthetic solutions containing more than one foreign ions were also analysed with the help of these indicators at pH 1.0. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS

Taken	Found Fe ³⁺ mg	
	Salicyl-aldoxime	β -Resoreylaldoxime
1. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +50 mg Na ⁺ + 5 mg Ag ⁺	2.80	2.82
2. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +10 mg Pd ²⁺ + 50 mg K ⁺	2.80	2.80
3. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +15 mg Ca ²⁺ + 25 mg NH ₄ ⁺	2.82	2.80
4. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ + 5 mg Sr ²⁺ + 5 mg Ba ²⁺	2.80	2.80
5. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Fe ²⁺ + 5 mg Al ³⁺	2.80	2.77
6. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ + 1 mg Co ²⁺ + 1 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80

Suggested procedure: Take 5 ml aliquot of solution containing ferric ions, bring the pH to 1.5, add four drops of 1.0% solution of indicator and titrate against 0.01M solution of NTA to light yellow colour.

Applications: An indigenous iron ore having the following percentage composition was also analysed by the suggested procedure.

Fe₂O₃ 92.8, Al₂O₃ 1.54, SiO₂ 3.07, CaO 0.3
TiO₂ 0.1, MgO 0.28, P 0.10, S 0.03

1.84 g of the ore was weighed accurately, the ore was brought into solution by standard method and diluted to 250 ml. A 2 ml aliquot of this solution was diluted to 100 ml and two 2 ml aliquots of the solution were then analysed as per the suggested procedure. The titre values of 0.01M, 6.82 ml and 6.84 ml NTA correspond to 3.81 mg and 3.82 mg respectively which are in good agreement with the calculated values of 3.82 mg.

The suggested indicators are superior to pyrocatechol violet and N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine in that titrations can be carried out in the pH range 1.0–1.5 and are more selective.

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